

BROMINATION OF ETHYL β -ARYLAMINOMETHYLENE -CYANOACETATES, -ACETOACETATES AND -MALONATES

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Bromination of ethyl β -anilinomethylene-cyanoacetate, -acetoacetate and -malonate has been investigated in chloroform and acetic acid in different proportions. The $\alpha\beta$ -dibromo derivative of ethyl β -anilinomethylene-cyanoacetate has been found to be more stable than that of the acetoacetate, while the corresponding malonate derivative seems to be highly unstable. Ethyl β -anilinomethylene-acetoacetate and -malonate are decomposed during bromination in chloroform.

It was shown by Dains and Griffin (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1917, 39, 963) that the monobromo product obtained by Dains (*Ber.*, 1902, 35, 2510) by bromination of ethyl β -anilinomethylene-cyanoacetate in glacial acetic acid was ethyl α -cyano- β -*p*-bromoanilinoacrylate. Dains, O'Brien and Johnson (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1916, 38, 1510) suggested that the aminomethylene compounds containing the grouping $>C:CH.NHR$ reacted also in the tautomeric form $>CH.CH:NR$. The dibromide obtained from the latter form may under the influence of solvents either lose its bromine entirely or undergo rearrangement, yielding a monobromo-substitution product and hydrogen bromide.

Bromination of ethyl β -arylaminomethylene-acetoacetates and -malonates and ethyl β -arylamino- β -carbethoxyacrylates in chloroform was found, with excess of bromine, to yield $\alpha\beta$ derivatives containing two or three bromine atoms in the nucleus (Mapara and Desai, this *Journal*, 1955, 32, 52). Chlorination of ethyl β -arylamino-methylene-malonates in chloroform by sulphuryl chloride was reported to furnish products having chlorine both in the nucleus and in the side chain (Upadhyaya and Desai, *Science & Culture*, 1955, 21, 37). But further work revealed that the products, thus obtained, were hydrobromides or hydrochlorides of the corresponding haloamines.

So the bromination of these esters was investigated further by varying (a) the proportion of bromine, (b) the solvent and (c) the concentration of the ester in the solvent employed. This investigation has brought to light the following facts:

(i) Bromination of ethyl β -anilinomethylene-cyanoacetate in chloroform affords the $\alpha\beta$ -dibromo derivative, whereas the bromination of the corresponding acetoacetate and malonate in chloroform leads to decomposition and formation of the hydrobromides of the bromoamines (cf. Mapara and Desai, *loc. cit.*). Further, bromination of the cyanoacetate with an equimolecular quantity of bromine furnishes ethyl β -*p*-bromoanilinomethylene-cyanoacetate, whereas under the same conditions, the acetoacetate affords a small quantity of ethyl $\alpha\beta$ -dibromo- β -*op*-dibromoanilinomethylene-acetoacetate (I).

(ii) The side-chain brominated derivatives of all the above esters are unstable and lose their side-chain bromine slowly on exposure, but rapidly on treatment with water. Such a derivative of ethyl β -anilinomethylene-cyanoacetate is, however, less unstable than that of the corresponding acetoacetate, whereas the corresponding malonate derivative is highly unstable and, hence, could not be investigated.

(iii) The amount of solvent and the reaction time are important factors, as their variations determine the nature of the products obtained. Thus, when ethyl β -anilinomethylene-cyanoacetate is treated with two or three moles of bromine in a large volume of chloroform or acetic acid, ethyl $\alpha\beta$ -dibromo- β -*p*-bromoanilinomethylene-cyanoacetate (II) is obtained; when, however, the bromination is carried out with excess of bromine in the minimum possible volume of the solvent, ethyl $\alpha\beta$ -dibromo- β -*o**p*-dibromoanilinomethylene-cyanoacetate (III) is produced. If the reaction mixture is allowed to stand for a very long time, the side chain begins to decompose and a small quantity of *sym*-tribromoaniline hydrobromide is precipitated.

(iv) All attempts to prepare ethyl $\alpha\beta$ -dibromo- β -*sym*-tribromoanilinomethylene-cyanoacetate or the corresponding product without the side-chain bromine failed.

(v) Ethyl β -*m*-nitroanilinomethylene-malonate could not be brominated even in glacial acetic acid without rupture of the side chain, and so 3-nitro-6-bromoaniline hydrobromide was obtained.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

Ethyl β -anilinomethylene-cyanoacetate was prepared by the method of Snyder and Jones (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1946, 68, 1253). Ethyl β -anilino- and β -*m*-nitroanilino-methylene-acetoacetates were prepared by heating together equimolecular quantities of ethyl ethoxymethylene-acetoacetate and aniline or *m*-nitroaniline in a steam-bath. Ethyl β -arylaminomethylene-malonates were prepared by the method of Duffin and Kendall (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1946, 893).

General Method of Bromination.—Bromine in chloroform or glacial acetic acid was slowly added to the ester solution in the same solvent. The reaction mixture was

allowed to stand at room temperature for the required period after which the separated product was filtered out, washed with a small amount of the solvent and dried. The yields registered varied from 30 to 34%. This product was then treated with water and in all such cases the liberated bromine from the side chain was estimated by Volhard's method.

Such a derivative of ethyl β -anilinomethylene-malonate, being highly unstable, lost the side-chain bromine so rapidly on isolation that it could not be investigated.

Bromination of ethyl β -anilinomethylene-acetoacetate formed ethyl $\alpha\beta$ -dibromo- β -*op*-dibromoanilino product, which was filtered off. The filtrate, when diluted with water, furnished a mixture of ethyl β -*p*-bromo- and ethyl β -*op*-dibromo-anilinomethylene-acetoacetates, which were separated by fractional crystallisation from alcohol.

The products were confirmed, wherever possible, by their mixed melting points with authentic specimens obtained by the condensation of the corresponding bromoamines and the esters. These products along with experimental conditions are described in Tables I and II.

TABLE I

Bromine taken.	Reaction time.	Bromo compounds.	M.P.	* Bromine.	
				Total.	Side-chain.
(1). Ethyl β -anilinomethylene-cyanoacetate (0.015 M) in CHCl_3 or acetic acid (100 c.c.).					
0.015M	3 days	Ethyl β - <i>p</i> -bromoanilinomethylene-cyanoacetate	151°	...	...
0.03M	Overnight	Ethyl $\alpha\beta$ -dibromo- β - <i>p</i> -bromoanilinomethylene-cyanoacetate $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{11}\text{O}_2\text{N}_2\text{Br}_3$	116°-18° (decomp.)	53% (52.74%)	35.27% (35.16%)
(2). Ethyl β -anilinomethylene-cyanoacetate (0.0185M) in CHCl_3 (25c.c.) or AcOH (35c.c.).					
0.074M	Do	Ethyl $\alpha\beta$ -dibromo- β - <i>op</i> -dibromoanilinomethylene-cyanoacetate $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{10}\text{O}_2\text{N}_2\text{Br}_4$	105°-109° with decomp.	60.02 (59.92)	30.00 (29.96)
(3). Ethyl β -anilinomethylene-acetoacetate and-malonate (0.015M) in CHCl_3 (100 c.c.).					
0.015M	Do	<i>p</i> -Bromoaniline hydrobromide	206° (decomp.)	...	...
0.060M	4 hours	<i>sym.</i> -Tribromoaniline hydrobromide	196° (decomp.)	...	...
(4). Ethyl β -anilinomethylene-acetoacetate (0.01M) in acetic acid (100 c.c.).					
0.01M	1 hour	Ethyl $\alpha\beta$ -dibromo- β - <i>op</i> -dibromoanilinomethylene-acetoacetate $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{13}\text{O}_2\text{NBr}_4$	94°-96° (decomp.)	58.38 (58.07)	29.06 (29.038)
(5). Ethyl β -anilinomethylene-malonate (0.015M) in acetic acid (100 c.c.).					
0.015M	½ hour	Ethyl β - <i>p</i> -bromoanilinomethylene-malonate	103°	...	...
0.03M	2 hours	Ethyl β - <i>op</i> -dibromoanilinomethylene-malonate $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{13}\text{O}_4\text{NBr}_3$	126°	37.85 (38.00)	
(6). Ethyl β - <i>m</i> -nitroanilinomethylene-acetoacetate (0.015M) in acetic acid (100 c.c.).					
0.045M	Overnight	Ethyl $\alpha\beta$ -dibromo- β -3-nitro(?)-bromoanilinomethylene-acetoacetate $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{13}\text{O}_5\text{N}_2\text{Br}_3$	97°-101° (decomp.)	46.00 (46.42)	30.54 (30.94)
(7). Ethyl β - <i>m</i> -nitroanilinomethylene-malonate (0.02M) in acetic acid (100 c.c.).					
0.06M	2 hours	3-Nitro-6-bromoaniline hydrobromide.	244° (decomp.).	...	...

* The figures in parenthesis refer to calculated values.

TABLE II

Parent substance.	Treatment with water. Resulting product & formula.	M.P.	% Bromine.	
			Found.	Calc.
1. Ethyl $\alpha\beta$ -dibromo- β - p -bromoanilinomethylene-cyanoacetate	Ethyl- β - p -bromoanilinomethylene-cyanoacetate	151°	...	...
2. Ethyl $\alpha\beta$ -dibromo- β - op -dibromoanilinomethylene-cyanoacetate	Ethyl β - op -dibromoanilinomethylene-cyanoacetate $C_{12}H_{10}O_2N_2Br_2$	199° (decomp.)	42.3	42.78
3. Ethyl $\alpha\beta$ -dibromo- β - op -dibromoanilinomethylene-acetoacetate	Ethyl β - op -dibromoanilinomethylene-acetoacetate $C_{13}H_{13}O_3NBr_2$	160°	40.70	40.92
4. Ethyl $\alpha\beta$ -dibromo- β -3-nitro-(?)-bromoanilinomethylene-acetoacetate	Ethyl β -3-nitro-(?)-bromoanilinomethylene-acetoacetate $C_{13}H_{13}O_3N_2Br$	143°	22.48	22.40

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